

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Adaptability and the Pivot Penalty in Science and Technology"

Evaluator 1 Andrew Kao David Reinstein

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ABSTRACT

We organized one evaluation of the paper: "Adaptability and the Pivot Penalty in Science and Technology"^[1]. From the evaluation: "This paper introduces a measurement framework to quantify how far researchers move from their existing research when producing new works. [It] applies this framework to scientific publications and patents and documents a phenomenon called the 'pivot penalty' ... the impact of new research steeply declining the further a researcher moves from their prior work. This finding holds across different researchers, fields, and measurements of research impact."

According to this evaluator, the paper's strengths include "its broad applicability, strong data, and policy implications ... Should the government and universities encourage researchers to address important but remote questions? Should scientists pursue the hotspots of the scientific landscape and adapt to demands driven by funding or other reasons?" The evaluator's concerns include "under-explored benefits of pivoting, alternative explanation[s] such as timing of rewards, evolving journal preferences, and the choice of journals over fields for analysis." To read this evaluation, please see the link below.

Evaluations1. [Evaluator 1](#)**Overall ratings**

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	80	4.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³ See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

This paper presents a novel framework for measuring the degree of departure from prior research in new works, documenting the "pivot penalty," where the impact of research declines as scientists venture further from their past focus. The strengths include its broad applicability, strong data, and policy implications. Concerns include under-explored benefits of pivoting, alternative explanation[s] such as timing of rewards, evolving journal preferences, and the choice of journals over fields for analysis.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1	
	Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁴	80	(70, 90)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	82	(74, 90)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	85	(78, 92)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁷	85	(78, 92)
Logic & communication ⁸	80	(71, 89)
Open, collaborative, replicable ⁹	90	(85, 95)
Real-world relevance 10 , 11	80	(70, 90)
Relevance to global priorities ^{12, 13}	80	(70, 90)

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1	
	Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 	

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim¹⁴	Belief in claim¹⁵	Suggested robustness checks¹⁶
Evaluator 1 Anonymous	["Pivot penalty": research impact declines sharply the further one moves from previous work.] ¹⁷	[Claim feels too strong; likely missing factors in the measurement framework.] ¹⁸	It might be helpful to see the promotion/funding of these pivoting scientists.

Evaluation managers' discussion

Why we chose this paper

Global crisis events are likely to bring large welfare implications (lives/years lost, suffering, productivity, threats to civilization, etc.) Scientific research may help us prepare for, avoid, and moderate the impact of these events. Sometimes (as in the case of COVID) pivoting and adaptive responses are called for. We might want to anticipate and pre-position researchers to address such potential crises, but preparation brings costs, particularly as we may have unknown unknowns/black swan events. We can plan better if we understand the

costs of research pivoting. This may also help us understand the best approaches to funding research and fostering productive research careers in a changing landscape. This could also inform governments and philanthropic funders that are considering motivating researchers to refocus their efforts on a concern (e.g., risks from artificial intelligence) that was not in their original portfolio.

From our internal notes:

Positives: novel, interesting and arguably counter-intuitive results which have wider implications

Negatives: focus on Covid where a lot of things were happening so it's like a case study (but that should be part of the evaluation)

Unjournal process notes, paper versions

The evaluation considered the August 2024 version of the paper, linked [here](#). Since then, the paper is reported to have been conditionally accepted in Nature. We ended the evaluation process early, with a single evaluation, in partial consideration of this. (See our discussion of when and how we evaluate journal-published papers [here](#).)

The authors shared an updated version, which we [link here](#). The authors note:

The paper is largely very much as it was, but there is now a methods section, extended figures section, and a slightly revamped Supplementary Information. These are now in separate pieces, as opposed to a unified document (e.g., each figure is a separate file). But again it's all largely the same.

We asked ChatGPT o1 to consider the updates to the paper,¹⁹ and it basically confirmed that the changes were small; the main results and methods seem unchanged. The most notable difference identified is “the authors go from “13,456 retractions” and ~146k treated researchers in the August version to “13,455 retractions” and ~165k treated researchers in the February version”. It is not clear what caused this change.²⁰

We next asked ChatGPT o1 to consider “1. Any mistakes/misunderstandings in the evaluation? 2. Any suggestions in the evaluation that seem to have been addressed by the February update (relative to August?)”. We added (some of) these as footnotes in the evaluation, giving the evaluator a chance to respond; they responded in a few places, noted below.²¹ (See o1 conversation [here](#).)

How we chose the evaluators — see footnote²²

Authors' planned response

The authors have been in communication with us and aim to respond to this evaluation. When they do, we will share it here. The paper has been accepted for publication in Nature, and they have agreed to an embargo on communication until its release.

Issues potentially meriting further evaluation²³

We raised a number of issues in vetting this paper that might be worth further consideration by readers and future evaluators and replicators. We list these below.

Caveat: As evaluators have not considered these in detail, and authors have not had a chance to respond yet, we are not asserting these as substantive critiques of the paper, just as avenues for potential inquiry.

1. Does self-selection into pivoting (or into COVID topics) bias the estimated penalty (for use in more general future contexts)?
2. (Relatedly) External generalisability beyond COVID: Do the pandemic funding conditions make the patterns special and unusual?
3. Are citation-based bibliometrics the *most appropriate available* welfare metric for policy? Are they highly relevant? (Normative consideration.)
4. *Statistical inference:* The main text of the paper presents very limited statistical inference (uncertainty bounds, hypothesis testing, etc.), although some of this is in the online appendix. This could merit further checking and consideration, considering the consistency of the test results and the narrative.

Other diagnostic and robustness considerations could be relevant. For instance, adjusting for multiple-hypothesis adjustments/false discovery rates/familywise error rates. Parallel-trend tests seem particularly important in this context (including for retraction and COVID DiD setups). Some parallel-trend tests and graphics are presented in the appendix: evaluation could consider whether these appropriately and formally tested in every case.

References

1. Hill, R., Yin, Y., Stein, C., Wang, X., Wang, D., & Jones, B. F. (2025). The pivot penalty in research. **Nature**. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09048-1> Preprint: arXiv:2107.06476.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2107.06476>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. ↵
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). ↵
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

≡

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only ≡

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

≡

7. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ≡

8. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ≡

9.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

≡

10.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

≡

11.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

12. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

13.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

14.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

15. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

16.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↵](#)

17. Evaluator wrote: *““pivot penalty,” where the impact of new research steeply declines the further a researcher moves from their prior work.”* [↵](#)

18. Evaluator wrote: *“As I mentioned in the evaluation, I feel the claim is still too strong, even with some empirical support. There should be something happening but overlooked in the measurement framework.”* [↵](#)

19. 7 Nov 2025: the previously shared link to the ChatGPT conversation no longer works. We're working to fix this. Let us know if you're interested and we'll share the content [↵](#)

20. Context: *“We first consider events that may push researchers away from an existing research stream. Specifically, prior research is sometimes revealed as incorrect or unreliable, which may encourage researchers who had been building on that work to move in new directions. Here we focus on paper retractions”* [↵](#)

21. 7 Nov 2025: the previously shared link to the ChatGPT conversation no longer works. We're working to fix this. Let us know if you're interested and we'll share the content [↵](#)

22.

We looked for

- Expertise in consideration and metrics/modeling of the similarity of research fields/topics/areas.
- Familiarity with the ‘push to work on Covid topics’ across a range of fields.
- Bibliometrics, grant-metrics, and measures of research impact.
- Interest in/work in metascience and research productivity/research production function.
- Understanding of statistics/statistical inference

[↵](#)

23. Evaluation managers: Use this section to list or explain issues that need further scrutiny, potentially by [“independent Unjournal evaluators”](#). These may be issues you suggested in your “manager’s notes”/“bespoke evaluation notes” or issues evaluators identified that they acknowledged they were not fully able to address. [↵](#)

References

1. Hill, R., Yin, Y., Stein, C., Wang, X., Wang, D., & Jones, B. F. (2021). *Adaptability and the Pivot Penalty in Science and Technology* (Version 2). Version 2. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2107.06476> ↵